

Activity 2 - machine-actionable DMP use cases

In the second workshop exercise, we'll define use cases for machine-actionable DMPs. We've proposed some high-level themes below, but we encourage you to expand on these and add further ideas based on your own priorities and needs. Feel free to split broad topics into smaller units or propose completely new areas for discussion.

We would also like to get a sense of the main topics of interest pre-workshop. Please note your top three preferences in the google form.

- **Utilising PIDs**
What persistent identifiers can be used and for what purpose? E.g. DOIs, grant IDs to pull award details into DMPs, ORCIDs, Funder IDs and Research Resource IDs to add data and link together outputs and research groups....
- **Evaluation and monitoring**
What can be done to monitor intentions stated in DMPs against actions undertaken. How can compliance and reporting be automated? (Others have used checklists and rubrics to evaluate understanding of concepts by researchers, etc.)
- **Repository use cases**
What information can be exchanged between DMPs and repositories? Can repositories be notified of data expected to be deposited, and, once a deposit is made, trigger the relevant DOI to be sent back and added to the DMP?
- **Institutional use cases**
How can the information held within DMPs help inform service delivery? What information needs to be pulled out (e.g., data volumes)? How can tagging / ontologies help identify relevant text if data is buried in free text?
- **Disciplinary tailoring and recommender systems**
What scope is there to plug into domain-specific services and information systems? Can knowing certain information (e.g., data type) lead to recommendations on relevant standards or repositories?
- **Publishing DMPs**
What integrations are desirable / possible to enable researchers to deposit/publish DMPs and obtain DOIs more seamlessly? What is the version of record and lifecycle for updates in the world of 'active' DMPs?
- **Data discovery and reuse**
How can the data within DMPs aid discovery and reuse of data? What information could be pulled out and exposed, e.g., data types, methods or instruments used, data licence, etc?
- **Interoperability with other research systems**
What other systems should connect with DMP tools and how (e.g., CRIS systems, active data storage, lab notebooks, repositories...)? What specific APIs or connections are needed (e.g., API to export DMP to Je-S, UK joint electronic grants system; ResearchFish output tracking system)?